

How to achieve gender parity in science? Providing global evidence on key educational and economic drivers

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Abstract

Gender parity in science depends on a complex interplay of social, economic and educational variables. In this study, we compile a longitudinal dataset at the country level combining scientific bibliographic data from Dimensions, with the World Bank Open Data (WBOA), and the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS). Our goal is to identify conditions and pathways that could lead to gender parity in different world regions, by applying time-series forecasting methods (ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing), along with correlation analysis and Bayesian networks. While results vary by region, one recurring recommendation emerging from our models is the need to increase the number of researchers and the percentage of women graduating in Engineering, Manufacturing, and Construction, as this appears to be a critical driver for reducing gender disparities in the scientific workforce.

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4 1. Introduction

5 Over the past decades, the representation of women¹ in academia has increased significantly.
6 In countries such as Serbia (European Commission, 2024), nowadays there are more women
7 than men working in science, and gender parity (often invoked as a prerequisite for gender
8 equality) has been reached in disciplines such as Health Sciences in Spain (Aramayona et al.,
9 2022). However, this positive trend is threatened by a backlash, a resistance to gender equality
10 that is leading to a decline in support for feminist initiatives (Williamson, 2020). This has led
11 to talk of “gender fatigue”, which encapsulates the idea that we, as a society, have already dealt
12 with some gender inequalities, thus we should move forward (Kelan, 2009).

13 Recent evidence does not support the statement that gender equality in science has been
14 achieved (Larivière et al., 2013; Jaramillo et al., 2025; Zhao et al., 2023). While women are no
15 longer systematically excluded from academia as in the past, discrimination has evolved into
16 new forms of segregation (Walby, 1990). This implies that while women have gained access
17 to academia, they do not experience the same opportunities or face the same constraints as their
18 men counterparts. For instance, in the representation of women as last author (González-
19 Álvarez & Sos-Peña, 2020) or corresponding author (Chinchilla-Rodríguez, et al., 2025),
20 citations in STEM (Kuchanskyi et al., 2023), collaborations (Morillo et al., 2025), presence in
21 higher academic ranks (e.g. Spoon et al., 2023), journal editorial boards presence (Burg et al.,
22 2022) or conference participation (Jones et al., 2014), amongst others.

23 These disparities suggest that achieving gender parity is not a straightforward process, but
24 rather one shaped by nuanced and systemic characteristics. Understanding gender parity
25 therefore requires complementing this concept with contextual information that captures the
26 mechanisms underlying it. In this paper, we aim to enrich the concept of gender parity by
27 integrating it with other gender-related indicators that allow for a more nuanced analysis of its
28 driving forces.

29 The present project has two main objectives. First, it aims to assess whether current country-
30 level trends are moving towards gender parity in science and over what time horizon this may
31 occur. Second, it seeks to identify the structural variables that are associated with higher or
32 lower levels of gender parity across regions. Together, these objectives could inform science
33 policy by highlighting structural patterns and conditions linked to different trajectories toward
34 gender parity. Using data from Dimensions, World Bank Open Data (WBOA) and the
35 UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) from 1990 until 2020, alongside methodologies such as
36 time-series forecasting techniques (ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing) and Bayesian

¹ Throughout this article, we use women/men to refer to gender rather than female/male. Quoted articles and names of variables are not modified; therefore, some of them may not follow this guideline.

1 Networks (BNs), we aim to examine how various factors intersect with the gender parity
2 indicator and to estimate when gender parity may be reached in academia, and under which
3 conditions.

4 2. Literature Review

5 Gender (in)equality in science

6 Notable gender differences exist in various aspects of the academic environment. These include
7 differences in authorship positions (i.e. Demaine, 2021), in productivity (i.e. Campbell &
8 Simberloff, 2022), citation impact (i.e. Wu, 2024), and the contributions that women authors
9 tend to do in research (i.e. Macaluso et al., 2016), amongst others. Some authors have looked
10 for the reasons as to why this happens and found that gender differences begin before entering
11 academia (i.e. Ceci et al., 2014). One widely used indicator to assess the extent to which there
12 are gender differences, is gender parity. In this paper, we focus specifically on this concept,
13 which can be defined as “concerns relative equality in terms of numbers and proportions of
14 women and men, girls and boys, and is often calculated as the ratio of female-to-male values
15 for a given indicator.” (EIGE, 2025). Building on this literature, our study focuses on gender
16 parity as an aggregate indicator, examining how it varies geographically and over time.

17
18 Gender parity in science has been studied from different angles. Some research has focused on
19 the consequences that lack of gender parity can have in science, including a homogeneous
20 workforce that reinforces a vicious cycle that limits women’s opportunities and negatively
21 affects their professional trajectories (i.e. Aiston & Jung, 2015). It has also been studied how a
22 lack of gender parity has implications for the nature and direction of the research produced, as
23 evidence shows that women investigate different topics than men (i.e. Ceci et al., 2014; Ruiz-
24 Baena et al., 2025) and are more inclined to integrate gender perspectives into their research
25 (i.e. Key & Sumner, 2019).

26
27 Generally, however, gender parity has been studied in a descriptive way at the discipline level
28 and at the country level. Since each discipline and country has their own cultural characteristics,
29 it is usual that an analysis focuses exclusively on one discipline and/or country. When looking
30 at research that focuses on gender parity in the different disciplines, although there are
31 geographical and sub-disciplinary variations, we find that literature generally finds a lack of
32 gender parity in STEM related fields, and a closer situation to parity in Social Sciences and
33 Humanities and Biological Sciences (e.g. Casad et al., 2021; Nygaard et al., 2022; Sugimoto
34 & Larivière, 2023).

35
36 For this research, we are particularly interested in the insight that the literature has on gender
37 parity in countries, at a more macro level. When looking at parity in authorships, we find that
38 women represent less than 30% of fractioned authorships globally (Larivière et al., 2013) and
39 a third of the researchers (UNESCO, 2024). At the country level we find reports like the She
40 Figures by the European Commission. The latest edition, from 2024, found that women in

1 Europe represent 34% of the total researchers, with data ranging from 50% (e.g. North
2 Macedonia, Serbia, Montenegro), to around 27-29% (e.g. Germany, Hungary, Czechia), and
3 even lower levels in countries such as Japan (17.8%) or South Korea (22.2%) (European
4 Commission, 2024). This wide cross-country variation highlights the need for comparative
5 approaches to better understand the structural conditions associated with parity trajectories.

6
7 Research also studies gender parity grouping countries according to different criteria. When
8 studying gender and science, the aggragation of countries is usually marked by geography (e.g.
9 using the World Bank classification, such as Momeni et al., 2022, or continents, such as Frehill
10 & Zippel, 2011), economic level (e.g. using OECD data, such as Stoet & Geary, 2018) or
11 cultural similarities usually based in language (such as Thelwall, 2020, or Bauer et al., 2012).
12 The She Figures itself studies the situation of gender in academia in the European Union.
13 Interestingly, Narasimhan (2021) found that as the wealth of a country increases, so does the
14 participation of women in science; and then it falls, marking a U-shaped curve, although there
15 are differences between developed and developing countries (Narasimhan, 2021).

16 Gender parity predictions in science

17 Gender equality has not yet been globally achieved, and gender parity is often used as a
18 reference point in assessing progress toward reducing gender imbalances in science. By
19 examining how gender parity evolves across countries and over time, and by situating these
20 trajectories within broader educational, economic, and scientific-system contexts, this study
21 aims to explore the structural configurations associated with different pathways toward parity.

22
23 Thus, we first want to analyse country-level trends moving towards gender parity and the
24 timeframe it may take to be reached. There are several methods to forecast expected growth.
25 First, there are classical statistical time-series models, including time-series decomposition
26 (used in Abdollahi, 2020 to forecast oil prices), exponential smoothing (used in Rao et al., 2023
27 to forecast energy demand in China), and ARIMA models (used in Njenga, 2024 to measure
28 domestic credit growth in Kenya), which focus on trend and autocorrelation in univariate series.
29 Then, there are regression-based approaches for longitudinal data, such as time-series
30 regression (used in Hertzog et al., 2024 to study suicide deaths associated with climate change),
31 vector autoregressive (VAR) models (used to measure the spread of COVID-19 in Rajab et al.,
32 2022), and linear mixed models (used to study the ice retreat of the Arctic sea in Horvath et al.,
33 2021). Third, there are machine-learning approaches, notably neural networks (used for rainfall
34 forecasting in Darji et al., 2015), which aim at capturing non-linear patterns.

35
36 Using bibliometric methods, some authors have explored these methodologies as well, asking
37 themselves when we will reach gender parity in science using predictive models. However, to
38 the best of our knowledge, these efforts remain few (Table 1). The most notorious attempt is
39 that of Holman et al. (2018). In their research, they use PubMed and arXiv databases to identify
40 STEMM fields that will not reach gender parity without intervention. Using linear mixed
41 models, they conclude that the gender gap is likely to persist for generations in some fields,
42 such as Surgery, Computer Science, Physics and Maths. Jemielniak & Wilamowski (2025)

1 forecasted gender parity in all fields using 2001-2021 Scopus data and saw that the pace of
 2 growth decreases over time. Additional studies have sought to predict gender parity in STEM.
 3 For instance, Wang et al. (2021) stated that the most optimistic predictions show that gender
 4 parity in Computer Science authorship will be reached after 2100, and Msosa et al. (2022)
 5 found that “the assumption that women are increasingly assuming positions once considered
 6 "male" roles, overcoming outdated stereotypes, and thriving and succeeding in the STEM
 7 profession on different continents is far from true” (p. 257). Lastly, López-Aguirre (2019)
 8 studied the post-war Colombian context and discovered that, all else being equal, gender parity
 9 will be reached in 10 years for the Humanities and it would take 150 years for Engineering.
 10 This study extends these works by combining forecasting with multivariate structural analysis
 11 which is not jointly addressed in prior studies.

12
 13 Table 1. Non-exhaustive studies predicting gender parity in science and reasons leading to it.

Study	Geographical Focus	Fields	Methods	Causal Forces	Data
Holman et al. (2018)	Global	STEMM	Linear mixed models	No	PubMed, arXiv, 2002-2016
Wang et al. (2021)	Global	Computer Science	ARIMA	No	Semantic Scholar, 1970-2019
Msosa et al., (2022)	Global	STEM	Correlation, Regression Analyses	Yes	UNESCO, 2013-2017
López-Aguirre (2019)	Colombia	All	Correlation, linear regression models	No	UIS, RICYT, OCyT, COLCIENCIAS, World Bank Data, 2000-2015
Jemielniak & Wilamowski (2025)	Global	All	Trend extrapolations	No	Scopus and CrossRef, 2001-2021

14
 15 However, these predictive efforts do not usually take into account factors external to academia
 16 and do not go beyond the number of men and women within it. It is crucial to acknowledge
 17 that science, and the dynamics surrounding gender parity within it, do not evolve in isolation.
 18 As a result, these models could run the risk of overlooking broader social, cultural, and
 19 economic contexts, and thus treating gender parity largely as an isolated academic outcome.
 20 Thus, as a second objective we want to identify key societal, educational and economic forces
 21 that lead to gender parity.

22
 23 Bayesian Networks (Pearl, 1995) are popular graphical tools that allow for the exploration of
 24 structural interdependencies within multivariate data. They are typically used to explore these
 25 relationships, and for predictions. They are common methods in numerous fields, such as health
 26 (Witteveen et al., 2018; Sesen et al., 2013; Arora et al., 2019), energy transition (Borunda et
 27 al., 2016; Leicester et al., 2016; Shi et al., 2024) and engineering (Moradi et al., 2022; Misirli
 28 & Bener, 2014; del Águila & del Sagrado, 2015). Bayesian Networks are increasingly
 29 employed in bibliometric data. For instance, Ibáñez et al. (2011) applied BNs to explore
 30 relationships among bibliometric indicators and found them useful for addressing bibliometric
 31 questions. Furthermore, Robinson-Garcia et al. (2020) used this methodology to predict

1 contributorships of researchers for given publications and Sun et al. (2023) employed it to
 2 examine the relationship between citation counts and potential influencing factors.

3 3. Methods

4 3.1 Data

5 In this study we analyse the percentage of women in science to forecast gender parity levels
 6 and understand the structural factors associated with such parity. To do so, we examine a total
 7 of 96,925,045 publications indexed in Dimensions between 1990 and 2021. Unlike Scopus or
 8 Web of Science, which emphasise the selection of certain scientific output, Dimensions
 9 prioritises comprehensiveness (Visser et al., 2021), offering, in principle, greater coverage of
 10 global scientific output. Based on this dataset, we identified 23,066,108 unique authors using
 11 the Dimensions Researcher ID. For analytical purposes, we focused exclusively on researchers
 12 with a minimum of five publications, ensuring the inclusion of authors with a consolidated
 13 publication record. The final sample comprises 8,247,978 authors.

14 To obtain data on various national statistics to enrich the data on the number of researchers by
 15 gender, we retrieved data from the [UNESCO Institute for Statistics](#) (UIS) and the [World Bank](#)
 16 [Open Data](#) (WBOD) platforms. The UIS database constitutes the official United Nations
 17 repository for country-level statistics in the fields of education, science, and culture. WBOD is
 18 an open-access database managed by the World Bank, which provides statistical data on
 19 various development indicators for countries worldwide. The datasets were collected in
 20 November 2023, covering the maximum available time span for each source: 1996–2021 for
 21 UIS and 1990–2021 for WBOD. Given the structure of the dataset, a maximum of 4,795
 22 observations is possible for each indicator. We extracted a set of specific indicators from both
 23 databases, as detailed in Table 2. It is important to note that the data series are incomplete for
 24 certain years and countries (see Appendix 1 for information on handling missing data). The
 25 number of available observations and the corresponding available observation percentage is
 26 reported in the last two columns of Table 2. It is noteworthy the high proportion of complete
 27 data for length of maternity leave and labor force participation rate, whereas information
 28 regarding proportion of time spent on unpaid domestic and care work is severely lacking.

29
 30 Table 2. List of variables collected from UIS and WBOD, with their number and percentage of
 31 observations out of all countries/years collected data.

Full list of variables	Abbreviation	Source	Observations (max. 4,795)	% of observations (100% = 4795)
Proportion of time spent on unpaid domestic and care work, female (% of 24 hour day)	Domestic	WBD	173	3.6%
Length of paid maternity leave (calendar days)	Mat. Leave	WBD	4,311	89.9%
Female share of graduates in Arts and Humanities programmes (% , tertiary)	Arts & Hum	WBD	1,227	25.6%

Female share of graduates in Business, Administration and Law programmes, tertiary (%)	Busi, Admin & Law	WBD	1,075	22.4%
Female share of graduates in Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries and Veterinary programmes (% tertiary)	Agri, Forest, Fish & Vete	WBD	1,158	24.2%
Female share of graduates from Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) programmes, tertiary (%)	STEM	WBD	1,058	22.1%
Female share of graduates in education (% tertiary)	Edu	WBD	1,228	25.6%
Female share of graduates in engineering, manufacturing and construction (% tertiary)	Engi, Manu & Const	WBD	1,181	24.6%
Female share of graduates in health and welfare (% tertiary)	Heal & Welf	WBD	1,229	25.6%
Female share of graduates in Information and Communication Technologies programmes, tertiary (%)	TIC	WBD	1,015	21.2%
Female share of graduates in Natural Sciences, Mathematics and Statistics programmes (% tertiary)	Natu, Math & Stat	WBD	1,034	21.6%
Female share of graduates in other fields than Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics programmes, tertiary (%)	Others	WBD	1,055	22.0%
Female share of graduates in services (% tertiary)	Servi	WBD	1,084	22.6%
Female share of graduates in Social Sciences, Journalism and Information programmes (% tertiary)	Social, Jour & Info	WBD	1,029	21.5%
Adolescents out of school, female (% of female lower secondary school age)	Adolescents	WBD	1,650	34.4%
School enrollment, primary (gross), gender parity index (GPI)	School	WBD	3,596	75.0%
Trained teachers in upper secondary education, female (% of female teachers)	Teachers	WBD	530	11.1%
Labor force participation rate, female (% of female population ages 15+) (modeled ILO estimate)	Labor Force	WBD	4,321	90.1%
Researchers in R&D (per million people)	Researchers million	WBD/UIS	1,199	25.0%
Research and development expenditure (% of GDP)	R&D	WBD/UIS	2,005	41.8%

1
2 Based on the collected data, we constructed a dataset comprising the following variables: year,
3 country, region, number of researchers, percentage of women researchers using Dimensions
4 data, and the additional analytical variables from UIS and WOBD. Each row in the dataset
5 corresponds to a unique year-country observation, with the relevant variables for that specific
6 context. The number of years for which data are available varies per country, depending on the
7 data availability in Dimensions. We included only those years for which researcher data were
8 available, for a given country, in Dimensions. For instance, in cases where Dimensions data
9 for a country were limited to three years, only those years were incorporated, regardless of data
10 availability in the UIS or WBOD sources. For Dimensions data quality purposes, we had to
11 limit our analysis until 2020.

12 3.2 Data processing

13 To be able to perform analyses focused on gender, we first assigned a gender to researcher
14 names extracted from the Dimensions database (Section 3.2.1). This step was necessary to
15 transform author-level metadata into analytically usable, gender-disaggregated indicators.
16 Another important step within the data processing was the interpolation and selection of

1 statistical data to address missing values (Section 3.2.2). Both procedures are described in
2 detail below.

3 3.2.1 Gender assignment

4 First, we assign gender to researchers' names from the Dimensions dataset. For each author we
5 have the first name, last name and affiliation, thus enabling the application of a gender
6 assignment algorithm. Gender was assigned to authors based on bibliographic data using the
7 WikiGenDex algorithm (González-Salmón & Robinson-García, 2024a), which draws upon
8 open data sources, primarily Wikidata and the World Gender Name Dictionary (WGND)
9 (Raffo, 2021). This algorithm integrates four name lists: (i) name–surname–Slavic country–
10 gender, (ii) name–country–gender, (iii) name–gender, and (iv) name–language–country–
11 gender. By cross-referencing these lists with author names from Dimensions, the algorithm
12 estimates the probability of a name being associated with a woman or a man. It takes into
13 account the country of origin, language, and national particularities in gender assignment
14 practices, including cases where surnames indicate gender, particularly in Slavic countries.

15 Figure 1. Flow of the gender assignment process.

16

17 WikiGenDex follows a sequential process (Figure 1). First, it separates author names based on
18 whether they originate from Slavic or non-Slavic countries. For non-Slavic countries, it applies
19 the name–country–gender list. For Slavic countries, it uses the name–surname–country–gender
20 list, which incorporates both first names and surnames, as surnames can encode gender in
21 Slavic countries. Names without assigned gender are subsequently processed by excluding
22 missing data and applying a name–gender list that disregards country of origin, assigning
23 gender when there is broad international consensus. Finally, a list based on WGND data is

1 applied, using country languages and language-specific names to infer gender. All previously
2 assigned names are merged in a final step.

3 Compared with other gender assignment algorithms, WikiGenDex favours precision over
4 recall, with an estimated 80% recall (González-Salmón et al., 2024b). Nonetheless, any
5 approach to gender assignment based on names is subject to limitations and potential biases.
6 Algorithms that infer gender from names treat gender as a binary variable, excluding non-
7 binary and other gender identities. Additionally, gender assignment algorithms exhibit uneven
8 performance across countries, with a well-documented lower accuracy and coverage for Asian
9 names.

10 3.2.2 Interpolation & data selection

11 We obtained the percentage of women researchers and the number of total researchers by
12 country and year from the Dimensions data. For the rest of the variables, we turned to UIS and
13 WBOD. When dealing with UIS and WBOD data we encountered issues related to missing
14 data, as depicted by Table 1. It is important to note that the lack of data does not always reflect
15 the same underlying cause. Several factors could contribute to data gaps, including limited
16 resources, political conflict, or a lack of institutional interest. In the context of gender data,
17 Criado Pérez, in her book *Invisible Women*, highlights how the failure to recognize the
18 importance of gender-disaggregated data hinders the production of research that benefits
19 society as a whole (Criado Pérez, 2019). Furthermore, some countries lack complete data
20 because they did not exist during the entire period under study ([World Bank Data](#), 2025).
21 Finally, the absence of China's data is notable.

22
23 To deal with the missing data we implemented a natural cubic spline interpolation. With this
24 kind of interpolation, a “series of unique cubic polynomials are fitted between each of the data
25 points, with the stipulation that the curve obtained be continuous and appear smooth”
26 (McKinley & Levine, 1998, p. 1). During this process, some interpolated values exceeded the
27 bounds of the indicator's support; for example, some interpolated percentage values exceeded
28 100. These values were removed. Likewise, any interpolated values that produced negative
29 numbers were also excluded from the dataset. Moreover, to assess the reliability of the
30 interpolation and investigate whether the high percentage of interpolated values introduces too
31 much noise, we calculated an error rate, which allowed us to investigate the performance of
32 interpolation using test data, as explained in the Appendix 1 (A.1). We identified different
33 patterns of missing data, and the performance analysis indicated different thresholds of
34 interpolation that were appropriate for different patterns. In this way, for each country we
35 interpolated a different proportion of data, and some data remained missing. Nonetheless, some
36 countries had so little data, that no interpolation technique could compensate for, and were
37 consequently excluded from the analysis.

38
39 Furthermore, to avoid excluding countries due to the absence of a single data point, we sought
40 to retrieve the missing information from alternative sources, such as research articles or policy
41 reports. This approach was applied only in a limited number of cases where the lack of one

1 variable would otherwise have led to the complete removal of a country from the dataset,
2 allowing us to preserve country coverage while maintaining data integrity. It is fully
3 documented to ensure transparency in Appendix A.2, which shows the countries and variables
4 for which this situation occurred, along with the method employed to address each case.

5
6 The process resulted in a final dataset comprising 17 variables and 81 countries, whose
7 distribution across regions is listed in Table 3. For the analysis we merged countries in the
8 regions, according to the World Bank classification. Notably, the regional distribution of
9 countries was not uniform, with an overrepresentation of Europe & Central Asia, North
10 America, and the Middle East & North Africa regions. In contrast, Sub-Saharan Africa is
11 underrepresented, containing only 17.02% of the countries of that region in the dataset. This
12 uneven regional representation reflects persistent inequalities in the availability of
13 internationally comparable data (Pedró et al., 2025).

14
15 Table 3. Number of countries per region and percentage they represent from each region.

Region	Number of countries	Percentage from region
East Asia & Pacific	8	30.7%
Europe & Central Asia	39	71.7%
Latin America & Caribbean	10	31.3%
Middle East & North Africa	11	52.4%
North America	2	100.0%
South Asia	3	37.5%
Sub-Saharan Africa	8	17.0%

16
17 As we did not have sufficient data points in North America (which includes just two countries,
18 resulting in 60 observations), we merged North America and Europe & Central Asia data.
19 Similarly, we merged South Asia data with East Asia & Pacific data. In this way we ensure
20 that the Bayesian Network Analysis is sufficiently robust.

21 3.3 Methodological design

22 To carry out the analysis, we first apply ARIMA and exponential smoothing models to
23 Dimensions data to forecast progress towards gender parity in science at the regional level. We
24 then incorporate additional statistical variables and, following a correlation analysis, estimate
25 Bayesian networks. These networks are used to identify structural conditions and
26 configurations associated with reaching a threshold of 50% women in science across regions.
27 Below, we explain these steps in more detail.

28 First, we forecast the number of women by using historical data from Dimensions alone. To
29 evaluate the models' performance, the data was split into a training set (from 1990 until 2015)
30 and a test set (from 2015 until 2020). We applied standard models: Autoregressive Integrated
31 Moving Average (ARIMA) and exponential smoothing methods (Hyndman &

1 Athanasopoulos, 2018). ARIMA models incorporate both past observations and errors from
2 previous time steps to refine predictions. The selection of parameters and the number of lagged
3 observations considered is typically determined through maximum likelihood estimation.
4 Exponential smoothing methods also rely on past data and assign exponentially decreasing
5 weights to past observations, prioritizing recent observations while diminishing the influence
6 of older ones. We applied both modelling techniques for our data using the forecast package in
7 R (Hyndman, 2024) and ended up choosing ARIMA for showing a better performance.

8 To account for the dependencies within the data, we computed a correlation matrix for the
9 variables in the dataset (excluding the year column). In order to analyse the relationship
10 between all variables and to further deepen the analysis, we used Bayesian Networks (BNs).
11 BNs are graphical models that capture dependencies between multiple variables. These
12 relationships are depicted by directed edges (arcs) connecting nodes, each corresponding to a
13 random variable. The network structure can be inferred from data under specific modelling
14 assumptions. BNs are widely used in various domains due to their flexibility and
15 interpretability (Scutari & Denis, 2021).

16 In this article, BNs help incorporate additional information beyond the number of researchers
17 by gender, such as women's enrolment in different levels and fields of education, investment
18 in R&D, amongst many others. With their use, we examine whether additional information can
19 enhance the understanding and prediction of gender parity. This approach captures not only the
20 relationships between gender parity and its potential determinants, but also the
21 interdependencies among those determinants themselves.

22 For implementation purposes, BN were estimated using Uninet and the visualization was done
23 with iGraph. Uninet is a tool that facilitates the modelling and representation of BNs. It also
24 enables the final predictive analysis central to our study. Uninet is an uncertainty analysis
25 software package that focuses on dependence modelling for high dimensional distributions.
26 The software is available at: <https://lighttwist-software.com/uninet/>. Uninet does not allow
27 missing values. Therefore, we performed a final round of interpolation using the previously
28 interpolated dataset, rather than the original data. Since this intermediate dataset already
29 exhibited substantially fewer missing values, this additional interpolation step ensured
30 compatibility with the software without introducing distortions associated with extensive
31 imputation.

32 For the predictive modelling of the Bayesian Networks, we employed the software Uninet as
33 well. Based on the fitted univariate distributions, this software also allowed us to condition on
34 a 50% share of women, serving as an operational definition of gender parity. It also allowed us
35 to analyse the configurations of variables associated with this threshold within a given region.
36 As the distributions' support is determined in Uninet by the range of observations, the share of
37 women in some regions could not have been conditioned at 50%. To overcome this challenge,
38 we fitted Weibull distributions to the variable of interest (percentage of women researchers)
39 for Latin America & the Caribbean, the Middle East & North Africa, and Sub-Saharan Africa,
40 as these regions required distributional modelling due to data limitations. For the remaining
41 regions, the empirical distribution functions were sufficient to perform the conditionalization

1 directly, without the need for employing a parametric distribution and its fitting. We further
 2 confirmed that the differences between the original data and the conditionalized one were
 3 significant using the Welch’s t-test.

4 4. Results

5 4.1 Overall description

6 Since 1990, the number of researchers has increased greatly (Figure 2). The share of women
 7 researchers has increased as well. In 1990, women represented 18.28% of researchers, in 2000
 8 it was 23.38%, in 2010 it was 27.14% and in 2020 28.94%, while the share of researchers with
 9 unknown gender also increases over time, reflecting both data expansion and limitations of
 10 name-based gender assignment (Table 4). These numbers, however, vary considerably by
 11 country. If we take, for instance, 2020, proportion of women researchers can differ
 12 considerably, from countries with low proportions (such as Japan or Germany with 18.11%
 13 and 31.28% of women researchers), to countries where gender parity is approached (such as
 14 Romania and Tunisia with 49.37% and 49.71% of women researchers). Despite this substantial
 15 increase, women remain a minority among researchers globally.

16 Table 4. Number of women, men and unknown gender of researchers and percentage of women
 17 globally, by year.

	1990	2000	2010	2020
Women	100,487	267,454	675,001	1,158,159
Men	403,784	756,276	1,394,713	1,929,223
Unknown	45,491	120,145	417,543	913,951
% Women	18.3%	23.4%	27.1%	28.9%

18 Figure 2. Number of researchers over time by gender aggregated across all countries.

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2 Figure 3 shows the global distribution of women researchers in 2020. Countries are shaded
 3 according to the proportion of women researchers, with darker tones indicating higher
 4 percentages. Overlaying pie charts in selected countries illustrate the distribution of men and
 5 women researchers in countries with proportions of women researchers above the global
 6 average of 28.94% (e.g., Portugal, Romania or Tunisia) or below it (e.g. Japan, Pakistan or
 7 Chile). This variation highlights the importance of adopting a global perspective, as focusing
 8 exclusively on Europe or the United States risks overlooking the distinct dynamics and
 9 challenges present in other countries and regions.

10 Figure 3. Percentage of women authors by country, 2020. Only those countries with >100
 11 researchers in the year 2020 are presented.

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2 4.2 Gender parity forecast

3 Given our objective of estimating when gender parity in science may be reached, we used
 4 ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing on our Dimensions data, first globally to test the models
 5 and then by region. To evaluate the performance of the models, the data have been split into a
 6 training and a test set, for which both the forecast (in blue) and the actual data (in red) is
 7 presented. The models also present the confidence intervals that capture the uncertainty of the
 8 predictions. Based on the historical data until 2015, both models tend to slightly overestimate
 9 the number of female researchers, as we can see in Figure 4 (to see figures corresponding to all
 10 regions, see Appendix A.3). The true values are, however, captured by the uncertainty intervals.
 11 The interval in ARIMA is relatively wide and accommodates both modest increases as well as
 12 stronger increases. Thus, we rely on ARIMA to produce regional forecasts.

13 Figure 4. ARIMA (A) and Exponential Smoothing (B) for all women researchers globally,
 14 1990-2020 (Forecast from 2015 until 2020).

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2 Now we apply ARIMA models to regional percentages (Figure 5). This approach allows us to
 3 estimate when gender parity may be reached in each region, assuming the continuation of
 4 observed trends in the share of women researchers. The results indicate that gender parity (50%
 5 women researchers) is projected to be reached in slightly more than a decade in Europe &
 6 Central Asia (2037), North America (2038), and Latin America & Caribbean (2039). The
 7 model further forecasts that gender parity in East Asia & Pacific is projected around 2054. For
 8 the remaining regions, nearly half a century remains before parity is achieved, with projected
 9 dates around 2072 for Sub-Saharan Africa, around 2073 for the Middle East & North Africa,
 10 and around 2080 for South Asia.

11 Figure 5. ARIMA forecasts, along with uncertainty bands, for all regions.

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2 We note that, although informative, these forecasts do not provide information on underlying
 3 factors that could lead to an increase/decrease of women in science or in gender parity. Thus,
 4 we aim at enriching these predictions with other variables, such as the percentage of graduates
 5 in STEM that are women or expenditure in R&D. We investigate whether this information can
 6 lead to additional insights into the potential increase of women in science.

7 4.3. Structural Determinants of Gender Parity

8 4.3.1. Correlation structures and multivariate dependencies

9 We first report correlation matrices using all variables for each region (Figure 6). The results
 10 reveal correlations among the variables across all regions, with stronger associations in North
 11 America and weaker ones in Latin America and the Caribbean. This gradient suggests that the
 12 structural relationships among the indicators vary by context, leading to more tightly connected
 13 patterns in the northern part of the American continent. The percentage of women also shows
 14 several positive and negative associations with other variables, indicating that gender
 15 composition interacts with broader demographic, economic, or institutional factors rather than
 16 operating independently. However, although these correlations are statistically observable,
 17 they are not sufficiently strong to justify the exclusion of any variable from the analysis.

1 Regional patterns reveal distinct correlation structures. A recurrent feature is the presence of
2 strong negative correlations across multiple regions. For instance, in East Asia, the number of
3 researchers is negatively correlated with the percentages of graduates in Business, while in
4 South Asia, it shows a negative correlation with women's labor force participation. In the
5 Middle East and North Africa, the number of days with paid maternity leave exhibits the
6 weakest association with the remaining variables, followed by the total number of researchers.
7 In Europe and Central Asia, the least connected variable is the share of GDP devoted to R&D.
8 In East Asia and the Pacific, the percentage of women graduating in Business shows a notably
9 strong relationship with several variables, while in Latin America and the Caribbean the
10 weakest links appear for the percentage of women graduates in Natural Sciences. North
11 America presents marked negative correlations for Business graduates, Natural Sciences
12 graduates, R&D expenditure, and researcher counts. In Sub-Saharan Africa, the most striking
13 pattern is the negative association between women's labor force participation and the rest of
14 the variables. At the global level, the structure aligns with these regional tendencies: the most
15 negatively correlated indicators are women's labor force participation and the number of
16 researchers, highlighting their distinct behaviour across contexts.

17 Overall, the analysis shows that the variables are interdependent, not only in relation to the
18 percentage of women but also among themselves. This multidimensional dependency structure
19 provided a clear justification for adopting Bayesian Networks, as they are specifically designed
20 to model complex systems where multiple variables are interrelated.

21 Figure 6. Correlation matrix by region for variables in Table 2 (abbreviations are in this table
22 as well).

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2 **4.3.2. Bayesian Network results and conditional configurations**

3 To further investigate the relationships among all variables, we modelled the data with
 4 Bayesian Networks (BNs, Table 5). We created BNs for each region, using the available data.
 5 As we can see in Figure 7, for the Bayesian Network for Europe & Central Asia (other networks
 6 can be found in Appendix A.4), each node corresponds to a variable, such as the percentage of
 7 women researchers (Perc Women), percentage of graduates from a field that are women (e.g.,
 8 Arts & Humanities, STEM, Health & Welfare), and socioeconomic factors (e.g., R&D, Mat.
 9 Leave). The meaning of the abbreviations are provided in table 2. The variable of interest, the
 10 percentage of women researchers (Perc Women), is in purple, educational variables are in
 11 yellow, gender-sensitive labour indicators in red, innovation systems metrics are in blue and
 12 scientific capacity variables are in green. Arcs indicate directed conditional dependencies
 13 (showing which conditional information contributes best to the joint distribution) and are
 14 learned from the data. Table 5 displays the mean and standard deviation for each variable. The
 15 network’s dense structure reflects the strong interconnectivity between policy variables and
 16 gender metrics, underscoring the structural complexity associated with gender parity.

Table 5. Mean and Standard deviation of variables on the Bayesian Network produced by Uninet.

Variables	East Asia & Pacific		Europe & Central Asia		Latin America & Caribbean		Middle East & North Africa		North America		South Asia		Sub-Saharan Africa	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Perc_Women_Researchers	27.1	9.23	35.5	9.18	32.1	8.61	23.2	9.24	31.4	9.05	24.7	9.14	23	9.13
N of researchers	21,000	35,700	16,500	28,900	7,200	17,400	2,310	5,940	26,600	68,800	18,700	33,500	1,050	1,990
Arts & Hum	51.6	55.4	61.6	44.9	48.4	90.9	42.3	60.5	61.6	43.8	50.1	48.4	30.2	116
Busi, Admin & Law	50.9	21.4	52.8	56.7	62.7	53.3	46.1	28.5	52.8	55.3	46.8	27.7	43.5	52.5
Agri, Forest, Fish & Vete	35.5	37.6	52	85.7	39.6	51.6			51.9	83.5	35.3	32.9	29.4	48.3
STEM			31.7	13.2	44.8	55.2	35.9	43.2	31.6	12.9			31.6	54.8
Edu	71.2	29.7	75.7	42.4	85.6	43.3	47.4	62.6	75.7	41.3	60.3	35.1	47.4	32.9
Engi, Manu & Const	44.5	78.7	25.3	40.6	44.9	81.9	31.5	93.6	25.1	39.6	43.8	72.4	7.88	83.5
Heal & Welf	58.7	32.4	62.4	87.9	71.3	43.7	72.4	60.1	63.3	85.7	39.6	57.5	69.2	83.9
Natu, Math & Stat			52.7	23.6	55.1	42.4	57.6	61.3	52.7	23			45	33.2
Servi			45.9	82.8	71.8	174	12.1	90.9	46.3	80.7				
Social, Jour & Info	61.5	34.7	72.3	61	59.4	62.2	63.3	59.7	72	70.9			51.4	82.6
TIC			31.8	41.8	53.2	73.8	30.3	53.7	31.3	41			33.4	112
Mat. Leave	80.6	34.2	143	68.8	103	18	67.6	35.7	139	70.9	83.9	31.7	84.7	27.9
Labor Partic	53.5	8.03	51.5	8.25	46.3	6.53	25.3	12.1	51.9	8.21	47.4	12.3	64.5	7.25
School	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0			1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0
Researchers million	2,310	2,200	2,420	2,230	378	336			2,490	2,200	1,720	2,100		
R&D	1.3	1.2	1.3	1.0	0.4	0.3			1.3	1.0	1.0	1.1		

1 In the case of Europe & Central Asia, we see that the percentage of women researchers receives
2 incoming arrows from the percentage of graduates in Business, Administration & Law and
3 Natural, Mathematics & Statistics that are women. Within the BN structure, this indicates
4 associations between these educational variables and the share of women researchers. Since
5 variables of other types do not show direct conditional links to the percentage of women
6 researchers, this pattern suggests that gender parity in this region is more closely related to
7 horizontal field distribution than to overall participation in academia. That is, the horizontal
8 distribution rather than the vertical (Tomassini, 2021). We observe that variables that influence
9 others are mainly the percentage of women graduating in STEM, Business, Administration &
10 Law, and Information & Communication sciences. On the other hand, those that exhibit more
11 dependencies with other variables are the percentage of women graduating in Natural,
12 Mathematics & Statistics and variables related to the scientific capacity of a country
13 (percentage of GDP spent in R&D and researchers per million inhabitants). It is noteworthy
14 that the variables referring to the percentage of women graduating in Services, the weeks of
15 paid maternity leave and school enrolment of girls are not connected to any other nodes,
16 suggesting a lack of conditional association with the percentage of women researchers or other
17 variables.

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19 Figure 7. Bayesian Network for Europe & Central Asia. Abbreviations can be found in table 2.

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In Appendix A.4 we can see the BNs for the other regions. Overall, we find that educational variables show the strongest conditional associations with the percentage of women in science. This may partly reflect the larger number of educational indicators included in our dataset. However, it is noteworthy that this pattern does not hold in Sub-Saharan Africa or Latin America & Caribbean. In these regions, the results point to a stronger role of vertical segregation, whereas in the other regions the main challenge lies in the horizontal segregation of women across fields. It is also interesting to see how Business, Administration & Law and Engineering, Manufacturing & Constructions had a big presence in terms of relationships within the network in most regions, suggesting that the percentage of women that graduate from those areas of knowledge have a high impact in the remainder of the socioeconomic sphere. Finally, the percentage of women researchers appears primarily as an outcome variable within the networks, rather than as a variable that exerts conditional influence on the rest of the system.

After fitting the BNs, we were able to conditionalize the variable of interest, that is, the percentage of women researchers in each region, at a specified level. This implies a diagnostic analysis, where we investigate the setting under which the variable of interest exhibits the parity

1 threshold level. Thus, we were able to see how other variables are estimated to shift in order to
2 reach 50% of women researchers (Table 6). Figure 8 illustrates how the values of various
3 variables could change, according to our model under the parity threshold scenario in the
4 region. Yellow dots indicate variables that would need to increase, while red dots indicate
5 variables that would need to decrease to reach 50% women researchers. And the distance from
6 the current values (dashed line) represents the amplitude of the estimated change for each
7 variable. The bottom-right area of the graph displays the variables that, globally, on average,
8 exhibit the largest deviations from current values under the parity scenario.

9 Figure 8. Percentual change after conditioning, with respect to the original data. Red dots are
10 negative changes; yellow dots are positive.

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Table 6. Mean and Standard deviation of variables on the Bayesian Network produced by Uninet after conditionalizing to 50% of women researchers.

Variables	East Asia & Pacific		Europe & Central Asia		Latin America & Caribbean		Middle East & North Africa		North America		South Asia		Sub-Saharan Africa	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
N of researchers	9,390	2,290	14,300	26,600	44,000	38,700	13,700	15,000	23,400	62,900	53,300	50,500	4,350	3,810
Arts & Hum	59.3	39.2	68.4	32.7	75.1	93.5	62.7	41.8	68.3	31.7	50.1	48.3	124	128
Busi, Admin & Law	49.8	21.5	80.8	49.8	52.4	44.2	46.1	28.5	80.2	49.2	70.7	31.3	54.6	51.2
Agri, Forest, Fish & Vete	23.8	47.6	50.8	84.5	48.4	51.9			50.8	82.5	47.8	21.5	28	47.3
STEM			36.4	13	29.1	26	35.9	43.1	36.3	12.7			42.7	57.4
Edu	53.2	33.6	89.9	51.9	80.4	38.3	88.5	28.3	89.5	51.1	93.9	42.9	49.5	33.4
Engi, Manu & Const	245	171	37.9	38	68.1	105	31.5	93.5	37.5	37.4	212	160	28.3	80.3
Heal & Welf	58	33	75.9	48.9	61.8	45.7	72.4	60	75.8	49.1	80.3	5.9	97.1	111
Natu, Math & Stat			70.1	27.7	57.1	42.9	81.2	67.6	69.8	27.3			61.4	35.6
Servi			45.9	82.7	71.8	174	11.6	91.1	46.3	80.6				
Social, Jour & Info	43.7	28.4	91.6	93.6	57.8	61.8	83.7	73.4	91	70.9			126	111
TIC			31.8	41.7	17.9	19.6	30.3	53.6	31.3	41			120	115
Mat. Leave	65	35.1	143	68.7	99.9	17.6	67.6	35.6	139	70.9	75.8	32	90.2	24.1
Labor Partic	52.1	7.43	51.5	8.24	49.9	5.66	30.2	13.5	51.9	8.2	63.9	9.66	58.3	7.13
School	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0			1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.0
Researchers million	2,630	2,250	2,180	2,290	993	481			2,490	2,200	2,710	2,380		
R&D	0.8	1.0	1.1	0.9	0.7	0.3			1.1	1.0	2.0	1.4		

1 The employed BN regional models suggest that regions that exhibit the largest estimated
2 deviations from current values under the conditional parity scenario are Latin America &
3 Caribbean, South Asia, and Sub-Saharan Africa. In contrast, conditional estimates indicate that
4 East Asia & Pacific, Europe & Central Asia, the Middle East & North Africa, and North
5 America require, comparatively, modest changes. For the Europe & Central Asia dataset, it is
6 noteworthy that, since some countries have already surpassed the threshold of having more
7 than 50% of women researchers (such as Republic of North Macedonia in 2019 and 2020,
8 Kazakhstan in 2020), achieving parity may imply decreasing current levels of other variables.
9 Although the unconditional mean is not higher than 50% in any region, it is important to take
10 that into account when interpreting the results.

11 The model presents a similar arrangement in Europe & Central Asia and North America. In
12 these regions, variables requiring adjustment appear to increase slightly. For Europe & Central
13 Asia and North America these include mainly an increase in the shares of women graduates in
14 Business, Administration & Law and Engineering, Manufacturing & Construction.

15 Then, Latin America & Caribbean and the Middle East & North Africa stand out for the
16 requirement to considerably increase the number of researchers, more than in any other region.
17 In the Middle East & North Africa, bigger increases also appear necessary in the share of
18 graduates in Education and Arts & Humanities that are women. Latin America & Caribbean
19 exhibits a more complex scenario. Conditional estimates suggest that some indicators would
20 need to increase, while others would need to decline to reach gender parity. The shares of
21 women graduates in TIC and STEM appear to require decreases, whereas the number of
22 researchers, researchers per million inhabitants, R&D expenditure, and the shares of women
23 graduates in Arts and Humanities and Engineering, Manufacturing and Construction would
24 need to increase.

25 In South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa, achieving gender parity appears to be associated with
26 a substantial rise in the number of researchers, although the increase would not need to be as
27 large as in the aforementioned regions. South Asia would require marked increases in the
28 number of researchers and percentage of graduates in Engineering, Manufacturing &
29 Construction. Moreover, increases would be needed in the percentage of graduates in Health
30 & Welfare that are women, percentage of GDP spent in R&D, number of researchers per million
31 inhabitants, percentage of graduates in Education and in Business, Administration & Law that
32 are women. Sub-Saharan Africa shows a similar pattern, with notable projected increases in
33 the number of researchers and in the proportion of women graduates in Arts and Humanities,
34 TIC, Engineering, Manufacturing & Construction, and Social Sciences, Journalism &
35 Information.

36 East Asia & Pacific shows a different pattern. In this region, most indicators appear to reflect
37 minimal changes necessary to achieve gender parity, with the exception of the number of
38 graduates in Engineering, Manufacturing & Construction that are women, which would need
39 to increase substantially. Conditional projections indicate that higher percentages of female
40 researchers are associated with reductions in the number of researchers, R&D expenditure, and
41 the share of women graduates in Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries & Veterinary fields. These

1 inferences result from the negative correlation between these variables and the percentage of
2 female researchers. The negative correlations reflect, for example, the challenges in sustaining
3 high(er) percentages of female researchers when the number of researchers increases, as
4 captured by the historical data.

5 When analysing by variables instead of by regions, the largest projected adjustments concern
6 the number of researchers, the shares of women graduates in Engineering, Manufacturing &
7 Construction, Arts & Humanities, and TIC, as well as researchers per million inhabitants. It is
8 noteworthy that some variables have not appeared during this conditional analysis: the share
9 of women graduates in Services, the duration of paid maternity leave, women’s labour force
10 participation, and girls’ school enrolment. These indicators appear less central in the model’s
11 projections, and it is striking that most of them are not directly linked to educational pathways.
12 That is, those indicators that would need to change less in general are gender-sensitive labour
13 and scientific capacity ones.

14 5. Discussion

15 In this study, we have employed predictive models to estimate when gender parity in research
16 may be achieved, based on available data. However, we identified the need to enrich the data
17 on the number of women researchers with additional indicators in order to obtain a more
18 nuanced and comprehensive understanding. To address this, we developed Bayesian Networks
19 incorporating gender parity alongside other variables, enabling us to identify which factors may
20 be associated with progress toward gender parity in each region, and the extent of their potential
21 influence.

22 ARIMA offers useful forecasts, showing how gender parity in science could be achieved in
23 around 15 years in Europe & Central Asia, Latin America & Caribbean and North America; in
24 approximately 30 years in East Asia & Pacific and in around 50 years in Middle East & North
25 Africa, South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. These forecasts, however, answer the “when”
26 question, but not the “how” question. These limitations have also been noted in earlier
27 applications, such as Wang et al. (2021) and Nane et al. (2022), where temporal models alone
28 could not capture the structural complexity of the scientific system. By incorporating
29 correlation matrices and Bayesian Networks, we obtain a more detailed representation in which
30 educational variables show particularly strong associations in shaping women’s participation
31 in research in most regions.

32 We find that some variables have a direct conditional association within the BN structure on
33 the percentage of women researchers in a region. In particular, it is remarkable how the share
34 of women graduating in Business, Administration & Law and Engineering, Manufacturing &
35 Constructions play a key role in shaping the percentage of women researchers and a central
36 role in BNs in general in most regions. It is also interesting to see how the percentage of women
37 researchers is a variable that is influenced more than it influences, and this configuration results
38 solely from data-driven structure learning techniques rather than from a design choice. This

1 suggests that changes in other variables could have, via the employed BNs, influence on gender
2 parity.

3 When examining the changes required to achieve gender parity, the global model indicates that
4 educational and innovation-system indicators would require the most substantial adjustments
5 at the global level. In contrast, gender-sensitive labour variables and scientific capacity
6 indicators appear less influential in our global model's projections. This pattern echoes
7 Walby's (1990) argument that exclusion has largely been replaced by discrimination within the
8 labour system: vertical segregation giving way to horizontal segregation. Thus, the issue
9 nowadays lies less in admission of women to the scientific system than in the dynamics that
10 shape how women are distributed across its fields.

11 Regional results further suggest that trajectories toward parity differ: in Sub-Saharan Africa
12 and South Asia, educational indicators appear to have weaker predictive power, and conditional
13 estimates point to a stronger role for innovation and scientific-capacity variables. This should
14 not be interpreted as a sequential progression in which regions must first address one set of
15 inequalities and then advance to another. Rather, the patterns suggest that regions may follow
16 distinct pathways toward gender parity. We emphasize that this interpretation does not rely on
17 a developmentalist logic that assumes all regions move through the same stages or that
18 replicating the experiences of already industrialized regions would yield similar outcomes
19 elsewhere (Temin, 2023). Instead, the results indicate that each region faces a different
20 configuration of challenges, not a different level of development.

21 There are several limitations to this study. First, the dataset contains substantial gaps, and while
22 we made every effort to interpolate missing values where possible, we were constrained by the
23 availability of reliable data. A significant portion of the missing data pertains to countries in
24 the Global South, which limits the generalizability of our findings. Moreover, the choice to
25 work with national and regional aggregates necessarily obscures within-country disparities that
26 future research could explore in greater detail. Second, there are many variables that could be
27 included here. We have done a selection of variables that could affect the percentage of women
28 researchers and were not redundant, but many more could be included. Third, gender
29 assignment algorithms present inherent limitations, as their accuracy varies across countries
30 and regions, and they rely on binary classifications that exclude non-binary identities, thereby
31 reinforcing a limited conceptualization of gender. Moreover, the fact that the share of
32 researchers with unknown gender increases over time deserves further investigation and should
33 be considered when analysing the results. Fourth, since the analysis relies on historical data,
34 Dynamic Bayesian Networks (DBNs) could also be applied. DBNs extend traditional Bayesian
35 Networks by explicitly incorporating temporal dependencies between variables across time
36 steps. However, this methodology remains relatively recent, and the resulting graphical
37 representations often present interpretability and stability challenges. Future work may
38 consider the implementation of DBNs as the underlying methods and tools are further
39 developed.

40 Despite these limitations, we believe our results provide valuable insights into the measures
41 needed to increase the representation of women researchers across regions. These findings

1 could inform policy decisions (for instance, by encouraging greater investment in increasing
2 the number of women entering Business, Engineering and related fields) and, in turn, contribute
3 to the development of a more inclusive and representative scientific workforce. Such a
4 transformation is essential if science is to reflect the diversity of humanity and fully leverage
5 its collective potential.

6 5.1 Policy implications and concluding remarks

7 Closing the gender gap in science is a complex endeavour rooted in subtle and structural forms
8 of bias. The study of gender in academia therefore presents significant conceptual and
9 methodological challenges. For this reason, this research shows that context needs to be
10 explicitly considered in at least two crucial ways. First, indicators such as gender parity require
11 contextualised interpretation. Analyses based solely on the absolute numbers or percentages of
12 women in science are insufficient when examined in isolation. Instead, these indicators should
13 be assessed alongside complementary measures that capture structural dynamics. Only through
14 such an integrated approach is it possible to obtain a more accurate understanding of the
15 mechanisms shaping gender inequalities and to identify where targeted interventions are most
16 likely to advance gender equity in academia.

17 Secondly, there is no universal measure for reaching gender equality in science, as such
18 measures must be sensitive to contextual and geographical differences. Bibliometric research
19 with a gender lens has traditionally focused on Europe and the United States, yet the resulting
20 findings are often implicitly treated as globally applicable, despite substantial regional
21 differences. From a policy perspective, closing the gender gap in science requires targeted and
22 context-specific policy interventions. For instance, our results highlight the relevance of
23 educational pathways in Engineering, Manufacturing & Construction studies in Europe &
24 Central Asia and North America; the role of R&D investment in South Asia and Latin America
25 & the Caribbean; and increasing the overall number of researchers in Latin America & the
26 Caribbean, the Middle East & North Africa, South Asia, and Sub-Saharan Africa.

27 To conclude, we emphasise the continued need for explicitly gender-sensitive policies in
28 science. The results demonstrate that gender differences persist and that the passage of time
29 alone and an increase in resources are insufficient to address existing inequalities. We can see
30 that in the East Asia & Pacific case, where the fact that having a high GDP spent in R&D or a
31 substantial number of researchers does not necessarily mean a higher share of women in
32 science, as politics have to be intentional and not gender-neutral to have positive gendered
33 consequences, in line with Steinþórsdóttir et al. (2020). Consequently, gender must be
34 incorporated as a central analytical and decision-making variable in science policy, as failing
35 to do so risks obscuring structural dynamics that shape participation and outcomes.

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9 8. Author contribution statements

10 Elvira González-Salmón: Methodology, Software, Validation, Investigation, writing -
11 Original Draft, Visualization

12

13 Zaida Chinchilla-Rodríguez: Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision

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17 Nicolas Robinson-Garcia: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing - Review & Editing,
18 Supervision

19

20 9. Competing interest statements

21 Authors of this research have no competing interests.

22

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30

31 11. Data availability statements

32 Data underlying this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18403324>

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12. Appendixes

A.1 Calculation of error rate for interpolation

To assess how much data could be interpolated, we first calculated an error rate. This calculation was based on two variables with complete data across all years: the percentage of female researchers in Spain and the percentage of female labor force participation in Spain. We manually removed one value from each variable, interpolated it, and then calculated the error rate as the absolute value of the difference between the interpolated and actual values. We repeated this process by removing two values, then three, and continued incrementally up to 31 observations.

However, we did not remove values randomly; instead, we followed patterns previously identified in the data. We observed that missing data could occur in seven distinct patterns:

A. Latest: Data is missing only for the most recent year(s). If multiple years are missing, they must be consecutive and immediately precede the last year.

- a. Examples:
 - i. Only 2020 is missing
 - ii. 2020 and 2019 are missing
 - iii. 2020, 2019, 2018 and 2017 are missing

- b. Non-examples:
 - i. 2020, 2019 and 2017 are missing

B. Earliest: Data is missing only for the earliest year(s). If more years are missing, they must be consecutive and immediately follow the first year.

- a. Examples:
 - i. Only 1990 is missing
 - ii. 1990 and 1991 are missing
 - iii. 1990, 1991, 1992 and 1993 are missing

- b. Non-examples:
 - i. 1990, 1991 and 1993 are missing.

C. Middle: Data is missing for years in the middle of the series, but both the earliest and latest years are present.

- a. Examples:
 - i. 2015 is missing
 - ii. 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003 are missing

- b. Non-examples:
 - i. 2015 and 1990 are missing
 - ii. 2015 and 2020 are missing

D. Latest & Middle: Data is missing for years in the middle of the series, and the most recent year (or consecutive recent years) is also missing.

- a. Examples:

- 1 i. 2018 and 2020 are missing
- 2 ii. 1993, 1999, 2000, 2007, 2018, 2019 and 2020 are missing
- 3 E. Earliest & Middle: Data is missing for the earliest year (or consecutive earliest years)
- 4 and for some middle years, but the latest year is present.
- 5 a. Examples:
- 6 i. 1990 and 2017 are missing
- 7 ii. 1990, 1991, 1993, 1999, 2000, 2007 and 2018 are missing
- 8 F. Latest, Earliest & Middle: Data is missing for the earliest, latest, and some middle
- 9 years.
- 10 a. Examples:
- 11 i. 1990, 2001 and 2020 are missing
- 12 ii. 1990, 1991, 2002, 2004, 2019 and 2020 are missing
- 13 G. Latest & Earliest: Both the earliest and latest year(s) are missing, but no middle years
- 14 are missing randomly. Missing years must be consecutive to either the first or last
- 15 year.
- 16 a. Examples:
- 17 i. Both 1990 and 2020 are missing.
- 18 ii. 1990, 1991, 2019, and 2020 are missing.

20 Below we provide a visual representation of each type of missing data (table A). We
 21 calculated the error rate for each of the seven patterns of missing data. As the analysis was
 22 conducted using two variables, we obtained fourteen different error rates. This variation
 23 occurred because the error rates differed slightly between the two variables examined: the
 24 percentage of women researchers and the percentage of female labor force participation. In
 25 cases where the error rates diverged, we selected the lower error rate as the standard
 26 conservative criterion to guide the interpolation of other variables. Additionally, we
 27 established a threshold: when the error rate reached 10, it represented the maximum
 28 acceptable limit for interpolation.

30 Table A. Patterns of missing data (A - latest years missing, B - earliest years missing, C -
 31 middle years missing, D - latest and middle years missing, E - earliest and middle years
 32 missing, F - earliest, latest and middle years missing, G - latest and earliest years missing).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
	Latest	Earliest	Middle	Latest & Middle	Earliest & Middle	Latest, Earliest & Middle	Latest & Earliest
2020	Missing	Data	Data	Missing	Data	Missing	Missing
2019	Missing	Data	Data	Data	Data	Data	Missing
2018	Missing	Data	Data	Data	Data	Data	Data
2017	Data	Data	Missing	Missing	Missing	Missing	Data
2016	Data	Data	Missing	Missing	Missing	Missing	Data
2015	Data	Data	Data	Data	Data	Data	Data

2014	Data	Data	Missing	Missing	Missing	Missing	Data
2013	Data	Data	Data	Data	Data	Data	Data
2012	Data	Missing	Data	Data	Data	Data	Missing
2011	Data	Missing	Missing	Missing	Missing	Missing	Missing
2010	Data	Missing	Data	Data	Missing	Missing	Missing

Below, we present an example of the error rate calculated when values were missing randomly in the middle of the time series (Middle). As shown in Figure A.1.1, the error rate remained relatively stable until more than 20 values were interpolated. For the percentage of women researchers, it was possible to interpolate up to 26 missing values without the error rate exceeding 2. However, for the percentage of female labor force participation, the error rate surpassed 15 after interpolating 24 missing values. Therefore, we established 24 as the maximum number of values that could be interpolated when data were missing randomly in the middle (Middle pattern).

Figure A.1.1 Error rate (y axis) for pattern C (middle values missing), depending on the number of excluded observations (x axis) for percentage female researchers in Spain (left) and percentage of Female labor force participation in Spain (right).

Table B reflects the maximum number of values that could be interpolated for the percentage female researchers and percentage female labor force participation, assuming a dataset spanning 32 years (1990-2021). For each type of missing data, we chose the lowest value as the maximum number of data points that we could interpolate. For instance, for the pattern “Latest”, we could interpolate 11 values for percentage of female researchers and 12 for the percentage of female labor force participation. To keep it robust, we chose 11 as the maximum number of years we could interpolate. We did the same for all missing data patterns. This ensured that interpolation limits were not driven by the most favorable case.

Table B. Number of values interpolated in percentage of female researchers and percentage of female force participation variables before +-10 error rate was reached. The lowest number is shown in bold, and the final column reports the corresponding percentage of interpolable data points.

Type of missing data	Nº of values interpolated before +-10 error rate in % Female researchers	Nº of values interpolated before +-10 error rate in % Female labor force	% of values that represents
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		participation	
Latest	11	12	34.37%
Earliest	6	8	18.75%
Middle	30	23	71.87%
Latest & Middle	30	30	93.75%
Earliest & Middle	30	15	46,87%
Latest, earliest & middle	30	30	93.75%
Latest & earliest	20	20	62.5%

1

2 However, as previously mentioned, not all countries had complete data for the full period of
3 analysis, due to gaps in the Dimensions database. In some cases, data were available for only
4 10 years. Therefore, we calculated the percentage of observations that could be interpolated
5 for each country, based on the number of years with available data. Table C presents these
6 results. For example, if a country had all years of data available and it was possible to
7 interpolate 11 values, this represented 34.37% of the total observations (Table B). Then, for
8 countries with 16 years of data, a maximum of 5 interpolated values was established, and so
9 on (Table C)

10

11 Table C. Number of data points we could interpolate for each variable given the number of total years
12 and the missing pattern (L - latest years missing, E - earliest years missing, M - middle years missing,
13 L, E - latest and middle years missing, L, E - latest and earliest years missing, E, M - earliest and
14 middle years missing, L, E, M - earliest, latest and middle years missing).

N° of years	L (34,37%)	E (18,75%)	M (71,87%)	L, E (62,5%)	L, M (93,75%)	E, M (46,87%)	L, E, M (93,75%)
1	0,34	0,19	0,72	0,63	0,94	0,47	0,94
2	0,69	0,38	1,44	1,25	1,88	0,94	1,88
3	1,03	0,56	2,16	1,88	2,81	1,41	2,81
4	1,38	0,75	2,88	2,50	3,75	1,88	3,75
5	1,72	0,94	3,59	3,13	4,69	2,34	4,69
6	2,06	1,13	4,31	3,75	5,63	2,81	5,63
7	2,41	1,31	5,03	4,38	6,56	3,28	6,56
8	2,75	1,50	5,75	5,00	7,50	3,75	7,50
9	3,09	1,69	6,47	5,63	8,44	4,22	8,44
10	3,44	1,88	7,19	6,25	9,38	4,69	9,38
11	3,78	2,06	7,91	6,88	10,31	5,16	10,31
12	4,13	2,25	8,63	7,50	11,25	5,63	11,25
13	4,47	2,44	9,34	8,13	12,19	6,09	12,19
14	4,81	2,63	10,06	8,75	13,13	6,56	13,13
15	5,16	2,81	10,78	9,38	14,06	7,03	14,06
16	5,50	3,00	11,50	10,00	15,00	7,50	15,00

17	5,84	3,19	12,22	10,63	15,94	7,97	15,94
18	6,19	3,38	12,94	11,25	16,88	8,44	16,88
19	6,53	3,56	13,66	11,88	17,81	8,91	17,81
20	6,88	3,75	14,38	12,50	18,75	9,38	18,75
21	7,22	3,94	15,09	13,13	19,69	9,84	19,69
22	7,56	4,13	15,81	13,75	20,63	10,31	20,63
23	7,91	4,31	16,53	14,38	21,56	10,78	21,56
24	8,25	4,50	17,25	15,00	22,50	11,25	22,50
25	8,59	4,69	17,97	15,63	23,44	11,72	23,44
26	8,94	4,88	18,69	16,25	24,38	12,19	24,38
27	9,28	5,06	19,41	16,88	25,31	12,66	25,31
28	9,63	5,25	20,13	17,50	26,25	13,13	26,25
29	9,97	5,44	20,84	18,13	27,19	13,59	27,19
30	10,31	5,63	21,56	18,75	28,13	14,06	28,13
31	10,66	5,81	22,28	19,38	29,06	14,53	29,06

1
2 Once we decided how much data we could interpolate in each case, we did a selection of
3 countries. We excluded territories that were not recognized as countries by the United
4 Nations. In addition, we removed countries for which there were fewer than 3000 researchers
5 recorded in the Dimensions database, as it was not feasible to draw reliable conclusions from
6 such limited data, and country-year combinations which resulted in less or equal 20
7 researchers. After applying these criteria, the final sample included 106 countries, which
8 were grouped by region as seen in table D. We use the World Bank division of countries.

9
10 Table D. Number of countries by region after excluding those with less than 3000
11 researchers.

	Total countries	Final count (>3000 researchers)	Final percentage
East Asia & Pacific	28	11	39,29%
Europe & Central Asia	52	42	80,77%
Latin America & Caribbean	33	14	42,42%
Middle East & North Africa	20	16	80%
North America	2	2	100%
South Asia	8	5	62,50%
Sub-Saharan Africa	46	16	34,78%
Total UN countries	189	106	56,08%

12
13 We decided to exclude variables for which data were available for fewer than 60% of
14 countries. These variables included: Proportion of time spent on unpaid domestic and care
15 work, female (% of 24 hour day), Adolescents out of school, female (% of female lower
16 secondary school age) and Trained teachers in upper secondary education, female (% of
17 female teachers).

1
 2 Additionally, we removed countries that had data for fewer than 70% of the 18 selected
 3 variables (i.e., fewer than 12 variables) from the 106 countries mentioned above. The
 4 countries excluded were as follows:

- 5 - Sub-Saharan Africa: Cote d'Ivoire (CI), Cameroon (CM), Malawi (MW), Nigeria
- 6 (NG), Senegal (SN), Seychelles (SY), Tanzania (TZ), Zambia (ZM)
- 7 - East Asia & Pacific: China (CN), Singapore (SG), Thailand (TH)
- 8 - Middle East & North Africa: Egypt (EG), Israel (IL), Iraq (IQ), Kuwait (KW)
- 9 - South Asia: Nepal (NP), Pakistan (PK)
- 10 - Europe & Central Asia: Russian Federation (RU)
- 11 - Latin America & Caribbean: Peru (PE), Venezuela (VE), Jamaica (JM), Trinidad and
- 12 Tobago (TT)

13
 14 In the data-cleaning process, each variable could only be retained within a region if all
 15 countries had valid observations for it. This requirement inevitably involved trade-offs
 16 between coverage and variable completeness: in several instances, preserving the maximum
 17 number of variables meant removing a country with missing data; in others, retaining the
 18 maximum number of countries required excluding a variable that was incomplete for too
 19 many countries and years. To prevent excessive loss on either side, we opted for a balanced
 20 approach. Some variables were excluded when they imposed an unreasonable reduction in
 21 country coverage in a region, and some countries were excluded when their missingness
 22 prevented the retention of otherwise informative variables within that region. The excluded
 23 countries and variables are:

- 24 ● East Asia & Pacific: STEM, TIC, Natural, services
- 25 ● Europe & Central Asia: Luxembourg (LU) and Bosnia (BA)
- 26 ● Middle East & North Africa: Agriculture, School enrollment, million researchers per
- 27 habitants and expenditure
- 28 ● South Asia: services, social sciences
- 29 ● Sub-Saharan Africa: Services, million inhabitants and expenditure; Sudan (SD)

30
 31 We ended up with 81 countries and 17 variables.

32 **A.2 Other sources for exceptional cases**

33 In a small number of exceptional cases, additional data-handling strategies were applied to
 34 preserve country coverage while maintaining consistency with the general interpolation rules
 35 described in Appendix A.1. Those tailored approaches to interpolate values are presented in
 36 Table E below.

37
 38 Table E. Sources of data used to obtain information for the selected countries and variables.

Country	Variable	Strategy	Additional sources
Indonesia (ID)	% GDP	Pattern transformation	Missing 20 out of 29 values, following the EM pattern. By transforming the pattern to LEM, interpolation was

			possible.
Moldova (MD)	School Enrollment	Pattern transformation	Missing 24 out of 31 values, following the E pattern. By transforming the pattern to LEM, interpolation was possible.
Serbia (RS)	School Enrollment	Conservative threshold extension	Missing 9 out of 31 values, following the E pattern. In theory, up to 6 values could be interpolated; however, greater flexibility was applied in this case.
Armenia (AM)	Researchers per million	Use of regional averages	Regional average data provided by WBOD were used to fill missing values.
Azerbaijan (AZ)	Researchers per million	Use of regional averages	Regional average data provided by WBOD were used to fill missing values.
Belarus (BY)	Researchers per million	Use of regional averages	Regional average data provided by WBOD were used to fill missing values.
Estonia (EE)	% GDP	Conservative threshold extension	Missing 8 out of 31 values, following the E pattern. In theory, up to 6 values could be interpolated; however, greater flexibility was applied.
Croatia (HR)	% GDP	Conservative threshold extension	Missing 9 out of 31 values, following the E pattern. In theory, up to 6 values could be interpolated; however, greater flexibility was applied.
Ireland (IE)	% GDP	Pattern transformation	Missing 16 out of 31 values, following the EM pattern. By transforming the pattern to LEM, interpolation was possible.
Cuba (CU)	STEM	Use of documented external sources	Data for 2016 indicated 39% of women in STEM. Additional evidence confirmed a value of 41% in 2024 (UNPD, 2024). Thus, we could expect 2017-2020 to be 40% and further interpolate.
Cuba (CU)	Maternity leave	Use of documented external sources	Evidence confirmed that, since at least 1974, maternity leave has been 18 weeks (126 days) (Powell 2017; International Labour Organization, 1998; Global Expansion, 2023; Inter-American Commission on Human Rights, 1983)
Cuba (CU)	Researchers per million	Use of regional averages	Regional average data provided by WBOD were used to fill missing values.
Brazil (BR)	% GDP	Conservative threshold extension	Missing 10 out of 31 values, following the E pattern. In theory, up to 6 values could be interpolated; however, greater flexibility was applied.
Bangladesh (BD)	Researchers per million	Use of regional averages	Regional average data provided by WBOD were used to fill missing values.
Bangladesh (BD)	% GDP	Use of documented external sources	Data were found for 2000–2016 and 2020 (Ferdaous & Rahman, 2017; The Business Standard, 2024).

1 A.3 ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing for all regions

2 Figure A.3.1. ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing for East Asia.

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4 Figure A.3.2. ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing for Europe & Central Asia.

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6 Figure A.3.3. ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing for Latin America & Caribbean.

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3 Figure A.3.4. ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing for Middle East & North Africa.

4

1 Figure A.3.5. ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing for North America.

2
3 Figure A.3.6. ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing for South Asia.

4
5 Figure A.3.7. ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing for Sub-Saharan Africa.

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4 A.4 Bayesian Networks by region

5 East Asia & Pacific

6 In East Asia & Pacific we find that the percentage of women researchers is strongly
 7 connected to the percentage of women graduating in Engineering, Manufacturing &
 8 Construction. We also see that those variables that are most strongly associated with the
 9 percentage of women researchers are, again, percentage of women graduating in Business,
 10 Administration & Law, in Arts & Humanities and in Engineering, Manufacturing &
 11 Constructions. On the other hand, those that show the strongest associations with other
 12 variables others are the percentage of GDP spent in R&D, the number of researchers and
 13 percentage of graduates in Social Sciences, Journalism & Information that are women.

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1 Figure A.4.1. Bayesian Network for East Asia & Pacific.

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7 Latin America & Caribbean

8 The percentage of women researchers in Latin America is closely associated with more
 9 factors: percentage of women graduating in TIC, labour force participation of women,
 10 percentage of GDP spent in R&D and the number of researchers per million inhabitants. The
 11 fact that those variables that are associated with the percentage of women researchers are
 12 mostly variables that are not educational is surprising, compared with other regions. Those
 13 variables that are most strongly connected to others are Business, Administration & Law,
 14 STEM and Arts & Humanities. Conversely, variables that are more influenced by other
 15 variables include the number of researchers, Engineering, Manufacturing & Constructions
 16 and Natural, Mathematics & Statistics.

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1 Figure A.4.2. Bayesian Network for Latin America & Caribbean.

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7 Middle East & North Africa

8 In the case of the Middle East, the percentage of women researchers is directly influenced by
 9 the percentage of graduates in Education that are women. This region is interesting, as the
 10 percentage of women researchers is modelled as to be indicative of another variable in return:
 11 that of the number of researchers. Most shaping variables are Business, Administration &
 12 Law and STEM. Those that, in turn, are heavily shaped by others include Services and
 13 Natural, Mathematics & Statistics, Social Sciences, Journalism & Information and labor force
 14 participation of women.

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1 Figure A.4.3. Bayesian Network for Middle East & North Africa.

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5 **North America**

6 North America data was merged with Europe & Central Asia to be able to perform the analysis.
 7 However, the BN differs slightly from the Europe & Central Asia one, suggesting that there are strong
 8 patterns in the North American data. We can see that the percentage of women researchers is
 9 associated with Business, Administration & Law and Natural, Mathematics & Statistics, a shift from
 10 the European and Central Asia BN. The main difference with the Europe & Central Asia network is
 11 the importance that the percentage of women graduates in Engineering, Manufacturing &
 12 Constructions has on shaping the number of researchers per million inhabitants, and the association
 13 that percentage of graduates in Education that are women has with Health & Welfare. School, Mat
 14 Leave and Servi appear to be unconnected with any other considered variable.

15

1 Figure A.4.4. Bayesian Network for North America.

2

3 South Asia

4 Data for South Asia also had to be merged, in this case with data from East Asia & Pacific.
 5 However, it shows its own patterns. In this case, the percentage of women researchers was
 6 not only associated with Engineering, Manufacturing & Constructions, but also by Health &
 7 Welfare and labour force participation of women. Moreover, this BN shows fewer
 8 relationships in general, with those variables that shape the network the most being
 9 percentage of graduates in Education that are women and Health & Welfare, and those more
 10 shaped by others being number of researchers and percentage of GDP spent on R&D. The
 11 fewer arcs however, can also be an artifact of the smaller sample size.

12

1 Figure A.4.5. Bayesian Network for South Asia.

2

3 Sub-Saharan Africa

4 The percentage of women researchers in Sub-Saharan Africa appears to be associated with
 5 many variables: Arts & Humanities, labor force participation of women and school
 6 enrollment of girls. In return, it shapes the number of researchers. Those variables that are
 7 more strongly connected to others are Arts & Humanities, Business, Administration & Law
 8 and Engineering, Manufacturing & Constructions. Those that are shaped by many variables
 9 are labor force participation of women, Health & Welfare and number of researchers.

10

